

A physically-grounded relation between the metallicity and the surface term affecting stellar oscillation frequencies

L. Manchon^{1,2}, K. Belkacem², R. Samadi², T. Sonoi^{2,3}, J. P. C. Marques¹, H.-G. Ludwig^{4,5}, E. Caffau⁵

¹Institut d’Astrophysique Spatiale, Université Paris-Sud, Orsay, France
email: louis.manchon@ias.u-psud.fr

²LESIA, Observatoire de Paris, PSL Research University, CNRS, Université Pierre et Marie Curie, Université Denis Diderot, 92195 Meudon, France

³Astronomical Institute, Tohoku University, 6-3 Aramaki Aza-Aoba, Aoba-ku Sendai, 980-8578, Japan

⁴Zentrum für Astronomie der Universität Heidelberg, Landessternwarte, Königstuhl 12, D-69117 Heidelberg, Germany

⁵GEPI, Observatoire de Paris, PSL University, CNRS, 5 Place Jules Janssen, 92190 Meudon, France

Abstract

The CoRoT and *Kepler* missions have provided high-quality measurements of the frequency spectra of solar-like pulsators, enabling us to probe stellar interiors with a very high degree of accuracy by comparing the observed and modeled frequencies. However, the frequencies computed with 1D models suffer from systematic errors related to the poor modeling of the uppermost layers of stars. These biases are what is commonly named the near surface effect. The dominant effect is thought to be related to the turbulent pressure that modifies the hydrostatic equilibrium and thus the frequencies. This has already been investigated using grids of 3D hydrodynamical simulations, however, the effect of metallicity has not been considered so far. We aim at studying the impact of metallicity on the surface effect, investigating its influence across the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, and providing a relation between the frequency differences and global parameters. We computed a grid of 29 patched 1D stellar models with the stellar evolution code CESTAM in which poorly modeled surface layers have been replaced by averaged stratification computed with the 3D hydrodynamical code CO⁵BOLD. It allowed us to study the dependence of the surface effect on the metallicity. We found that a correct way of accounting for it is to consider the surface Rosseland mean opacity. It allowed us to give a physically-grounded justification as well as a scaling relation for the frequency differences at ν_{\max} as a function of T_{eff} , $\log g$ and κ .

1 Introduction

The mismatch between the modelled and the observed stellar oscillation frequency is a great obstacle in the way of achieving the full potential of asteroseismology. Our understanding of stellar interiors has been tremendously improved thanks to the high quality spectra made available by the space-borne missions CoRoT (Baglin *et al.*, 2006; Michel *et al.*, 2008; Auvergne *et al.*, 2009) and *Kepler* (Borucki *et al.*, 2010). However, it has been known for about three decades (e.g. Dziembowski *et al.*, 1988) that, when comparing observed spectra to synthetic ones, systematic errors occur at high frequencies. This bias, called surface-effect, has been widely studied in the solar-case (Rosenthal *et al.*, 1995; Christensen-Dalsgaard & Thompson, 1997; Rosenthal *et al.*, 1999) and is caused by poor one-dimensional modelling of the near-surface layers.

In order to circumvent this issue, well-chosen frequency combinations are used to get rid of the surface-effect (e.g. Roxburgh & Vorontsov, 2003). The basic idea is to keep only the information coming from the inner parts of star while rejecting the one coming from the surface. However, an accurate comparison of the frequency spectra is still desirable in order to exploit the full capability of asteroseismology. To that end, two complementary approaches have been developed. The first one is to perform a posteriori correction of modelled frequencies. In order to do so, a handful of empirical corrections have been proposed (Kjeldsen *et al.*, 2008; Ball & Gizon, 2014; Sonoi *et al.*, 2015; Ball & Gizon, 2017), all making use of adjustable parameters. Because of its simplicity, this approach is now widely used and has proven to be a great improvement when inferring stellar parameters using individual frequencies (e.g. Lebreton & Goupil, 2014;

Silva Aguirre *et al.*, 2017). However, since the choice of the values of the adjustable parameters is not physically motivated, the uniqueness and correctness of the optimal model reproducing the observed frequencies is not guaranteed.

A second approach is to understand what physics implemented in our models fails to correctly reproduce the observed frequencies. The surface effects are understood to be the result of two distinct effects (e.g. Houdek *et al.*, 2017). On one hand, in 1D models, the turbulent pressure, arising from convective motions, is often omitted which causes discrepancies between the modelled and the actual medium in which acoustic oscillations propagate: these are the structural effects. On the other hand, if one wants to properly compute the properties of the modes in the stars, we need to take into account non-adiabatic effects (e.g. Balmforth, 1992; Houdek *et al.*, 2017) as well as the turbulent pressure (Sonoi *et al.*, 2017) term in the wave equation. These are usually neglected and it forms the modal effects. In order to take account for the turbulent pressure, thought to be the principal responsible for the surface-effect, the upper layers of a 1D model can be replaced by the horizontally averaged stratification of a well-chosen 3D hydrodynamical simulation. These are called patched models. Frequencies computed with the original 1D model (unpatched model; hereafter UPM) are then compared to the one (more realistic) computed with the patched model (hereafter PM) and it allows one for a theoretical study of the surface effect.

In Section 2 we provide a short description of our set of patched models and in Section 3 we derive a scaling relation reproducing the frequency differences at ν_{\max} as a function of $\Delta\nu$, T_{eff} , $\log g$ and the Rosseland opacity which enclosed the dependence in metallicity in a way that is independent

Figure 1: Frequency differences scaled by the frequency, taken at ν_{\max} against a scaling relation given by Rosenthal *et al.* (1999) (top panel) (with $\sigma = 0.89$ [μHz]) and a scaling relation given by Eq. (12) (with powers are left free (bottom panel) (with $\sigma_{\kappa} = 0.63$ [μHz]).

on the dominant opacity regime.

2 Set of patched models

In this section, we quickly describe our set of models. A complete description of the method of patched model and more details about the characteristics of each model can be found in Manchon *et al.* (2018).

We considered 29 models with effective temperature (T_{eff}) ranging from 4 500 K to 6 800 K, a surface gravity ($\log g$) ranging from 3.5 to 4.5, and a metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = \{-1.0, -0.5, +0.0, +0.5\}$. The 3D hydrodynamical models are taken from the CIFIST grid computed using the CO⁵BOLD code (see Ludwig *et al.*, 2009; Freytag *et al.*, 2012, for details). Those simulations reproduce the very first layers of the stellar photosphere as well as the superadiabatic region. The chemical mixture is based on the solar abundances of Grevesse & Sauval (1998) apart from CNO abundances which follow Asplund *et al.* (2005).

The 1D models have been computed using the stellar evolution code CESTAM (Morel, 1997; Marques *et al.*, 2013). It uses the equation of states, and opacities given by OPAL2005 (Rogers & Nayfonov, 2002; Iglesias & Rogers, 1996) and

implements standard mixing-length theory (Böhm-Vitense, 1958). No overshoot is considered in our models. We neglected diffusion processes, rotation and turbulent pressure. The atmosphere is recovered using the Eddington approximation. The helium abundance in 1D models is the same as in 3D models.

In this work, we only consider structural effects and oscillations are computed in the adiabatic approximation using the ADIPLS code (Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2011) for both UPM and PM. We assumed the gas Γ_1 approximation, which makes the approximation that the Lagrangian perturbations of gas pressure and turbulent pressure are equal (Rosenthal *et al.*, 1999; Sonoi *et al.*, 2017). In the present proceeding, we focus on the surface effect affecting radial modes. The case of non-radial and especially mixed-modes is quickly discussed in Manchon *et al.* (2018).

3 Influence of metallicity

3.1 Scaling of the frequency differences

Extra turbulent pressure extends the size of the resonant cavities and therefore decreases the mode frequencies for PM, leading to negative frequency differences $\delta\nu = \nu_{\text{PM}} - \nu_{\text{UPM}}$. $\delta\nu$ has been considered so far as a function of only two parameters: the effective temperature and the surface gravity. However, would $\delta\nu$ be affected by a change in the metallicity? Opacity, which mainly controls the radiative flux, is greatly determined by the abundance of heavy elements. The total flux being fixed, a change in the radiative flux is compensated by a change in the convective flux. Since the convective flux and the turbulent pressure scale as the convective velocity, a change in the metallicity would cause a change in the turbulent pressure and finally a change in $\delta\nu$.

In order to understand what determines the frequency differences between the UPM and the PM, Christensen-Dalsgaard & Thompson (1997); Rosenthal *et al.* (1999) (see also Goldreich *et al.*, 1991; Balmforth *et al.*, 1996) have adopted a perturbative approach to express the frequency differences:

$$\frac{\delta\nu}{\nu} = \int_0^R \left[\tilde{K}_{c^2, v}^{nl} \frac{\delta_m c^2}{c^2} + \tilde{K}_{v, c^2}^{nl} \frac{\delta_m v}{v} \right] dr \quad (1)$$

$$\simeq \int_0^R \tilde{K}_{v, c^2}^{nl} \frac{\delta_m v}{v} dr \quad (2)$$

$$\simeq \frac{\Delta\nu \Delta r}{c_{\text{ph}}}, \quad (3)$$

where c is the adiabatic sound speed, the variable v is defined by $v = \Gamma_1/c$, $\tilde{K}_{c^2, v}^{nl}$ and \tilde{K}_{v, c^2}^{nl} are the kernels that can be determined from eigenfunctions, $\delta_m c^2$ and $\delta_m v$ are the Lagrangian differences of c^2 and v , respectively, at fixed mass. In the last line, $\Delta\nu$ is the asymptotic large frequency separation, $\Delta r = R_{\text{PM}} - R_{\text{UPM}}$ is the elevation, and c_{ph} the photospheric sound speed.

This relation has been previously tested by Sonoi *et al.* (2015) at solar metallicity using surface effect derived with the same method. For our set of models, *i.e.* with solar- and non-solar-metallicity models, it turns out that Eq. 3 reproduces the overall scale of the surface effect (such as in Fig. 1, top panel, were the surface effect is considered to be the frequency differences at ν_{\max}).

3.2 Impact of the metallicity on the frequency differences at ν_{\max}

With Eq. (3), we do not have a clear view on how the metallicity impacts the surface effect. To that aim, we need to determine a relation between frequency differences at ν_{\max} and global parameters of the models. However, it can be shown that using directly the metallicity does not lead to a clear trend between the surface term and metallicity (see Manchon *et al.*, 2018). Indeed, we have shown that the metallicity acts on the surface effect through the opacity. The dependence of the opacity on the metallicity and on the temperature is not the same regarding which is the dominant opacity mechanism. Therefore, the relation between $\delta\nu/\nu$ and Z is not trivial and it is easier to replace the dependence in $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ by a dependence in the Rosseland opacity κ as a global parameter in addition to the effective temperature and to the surface gravity (in the following, the photosphere is defined as the radius at which $T = T_{\text{eff}}$).

Let us begin by considering the elevation Δr which must be expressed as a function of these global parameters. Using the hydrostatic equilibrium equation, it reads

$$\Delta r = \int_0^{R_{\text{PM}}} H_p^{\text{PM}} \frac{dp_{\text{tot}}}{p_{\text{tot}}} - \int_0^{R_{\text{UPM}}} H_p^{\text{UPM}} \frac{dp_g}{p_g}, \quad (4)$$

where H_p^{PM} and H_p^{UPM} are the pressure scale heights at the photosphere associated with the patched and unpatched models, p_{tot} is the total pressure such as $p_{\text{tot}} = p_{\text{turb}} + p_g$ with p_{turb} and p_g the turbulent and gas pressure, respectively. We further assume that $H_p^{\text{PM}} \simeq H_p^{\text{UPM}}$ and $p_{\text{turb}}/p_{\text{tot}} \ll 1$ and therefore, one can approximate Eq. (4) by

$$\Delta r \simeq H_p^{\text{PM}} \frac{p_{\text{turb}}}{p_{\text{tot}}}. \quad (5)$$

Finally, since the pressure scale-height scales as T_{eff}/g , the elevation scales as $\Delta r \propto (T_{\text{eff}} p_{\text{turb}})/(gp_g)$.

To go further, we need to find an expression for p_{turb}/p_g . Near the photosphere, the turbulent pressure can be written as

$$p_{\text{turb}} = \rho v_{\text{conv}}^2, \quad (6)$$

where v_{conv} is the vertical component of the convective velocity. We now need an expression for this velocity and for the density. Assuming a standard Eddington grey atmosphere, the optical depth is approximated by $\tau = H_p \rho \kappa$, and in the Eddington approximation, we have $\tau = 2/3$ at the bottom of the photosphere. Then:

$$\rho \propto \frac{g}{T_{\text{eff}} \kappa}. \quad (7)$$

As for finding an expression for v_{conv} , we note that $F_{\text{tot}} = F_{\text{rad}} + F_{\text{conv}}$, with F_{rad} and F_{conv} the radiative and convective component of the total energy flux respectively. The convective flux is proportional to the kinetic energy flux (as shown for instance within the MLT framework). Then,

$$\rho v_{\text{conv}}^3 \propto T_{\text{eff}}^4 \left(1 + \frac{F_{\text{rad}}}{F_{\text{conv}}} \right)^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

The ratio $F_{\text{rad}}/F_{\text{conv}}$ is assumed to remain nearly constant from one model to another (cf. Fig. 2). Therefore, v_{conv} finally reads,

$$v_{\text{conv}}^2 \propto \frac{T_{\text{eff}}^{8/3}}{\rho^{2/3}}. \quad (9)$$

We checked the latter hypothesis with the data coming from the 3D simulations used to compute our grid of patched mod-

els. The results are displayed in Fig. 2 which show that, apart from some outliers, the values of $F_{\text{rad}}/F_{\text{conv}}$ does not diverge too much from the mean value.

Inserting the expressions of Eq. (7) and (9) into Eq. (6) leads to:

$$p_{\text{turb}} \propto \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff}\odot}} \right)^{7/3} \left(\frac{g}{g_{\odot}} \right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{\kappa}{\kappa_{\odot}} \right)^{-1/3}, \quad (10)$$

where $\kappa_{\odot} = 0.415 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$. From the perfect gas law for, $p_g \propto \rho T_{\text{eff}}$ and using Eq. (7), we can rewrite Δr as

$$\Delta r \propto \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff}\odot}} \right)^{10/3} \left(\frac{g}{g_{\odot}} \right)^{-5/3} \left(\frac{\kappa}{\kappa_{\odot}} \right)^{2/3}. \quad (11)$$

Replacing Δr into Eq. (3) one finally obtains the following estimate:

$$\frac{\delta\nu}{\nu} \propto \frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\odot}} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff}\odot}} \right)^{17/6} \left(\frac{g}{g_{\odot}} \right)^{-5/3} \left(\frac{\kappa}{\kappa_{\odot}} \right)^{2/3}. \quad (12)$$

This expression provides us with a simple relation between the frequency differences and global parameters. The dependence on the metallicity is embedded into the Rosseland mean opacity. This is done without any assumption on the dominant opacity regime. We note that it is possible to go further and to explicitly introduce the metallicity. For instance, in the vicinity of the solar effective temperature and gravity, the opacity is dominated by the H^- so that $\kappa \propto \rho^{-1/2} T_{\text{eff}}^9 Z$. However, given the wide range of effective temperatures and surface gravities of our grid of models, it is more relevant to keep the Rosseland mean opacity at $T = T_{\text{eff}}$ (surface opacity) as a global parameter. Indeed, the Rosseland mean opacity is a quantity available in any 1D stellar evolutionary code.

Then, using Eq. (12) as a guideline, we performed a fit where the powers of the temperature (p), gravity (q), and opacity (s) have been adjusted at $\nu = \nu_{\max}$ for each model. Figure 1, bottom panel, displays the result. This figure shows a very good agreement between exponents derived in Eq. (12) and the one actually obtained using our simulations. Consequently, this scaling can be used to provide a physically-grounded value for the parameters of the empirical correction function of the surface effect. Finally, we note that using the opacity instead of the metallicity allows us to take a detailed mixture into account.

In addition to our crude approximations, there are several potential sources of discrepancies between values predicted by Eq. (12) and the one calculated. First, we did not fix the helium abundance from one model to the other when varying the metallicity. The changing helium abundances have an impact both on the evolution of the model and on its opacity at the surface. However, the helium abundances $[\text{He}/\text{H}]$ range between -5.8×10^{-3} and $+1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ and should be a negligible source of uncertainty. Second, errors may come from the method we used to average the 3D stratifications. Indeed, since the Rosseland opacity is involved Eq. (12), it would be more precise to patch the models using a stratification averaged against the Rosseland optical depth instead of the actual geometrically averaged stratification, but this is beyond the scope of this paper and will be investigated in a forthcoming work.

4 Conclusion

Using the method of patched models that consists in replacing the poorly modelled surface layers of a 1D stellar

Figure 2: Ratio between F_{rad} and F_{conv} computed from the 3D simulations used to create our grid. Values are computed at the altitude in the atmosphere where $T = T_{\text{eff}}$. Labels of the models are defined in Manchon *et al.* (2018).

model by the more realistic horizontally averaged stratification computed from a 3D stellar model atmosphere, we constructed a grid of 29 patched and unpatched models. The models in this grid have effective temperature (T_{eff}) ranging from 4 500 K to 6 800 K, surface gravity ($\log g$) ranging from 3.5 to 4.5, and finally our grid includes four different metallicities: $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = \{-1.0, -0.5, +0.0, +0.5\}$. This grid allowed us to compute frequency differences, between the frequency spectrum of patched and unpatched models. The computed frequency differences only take into account the structural effect, the modal effect being left to a forthcoming work.

We presented a physically-grounded scaling relation able to reproduce with a very good precision the surface effect at ν_{max} , as a function of the effective temperature, the surface gravity and the Rosseland opacity which embeds the dependence on the metallicity. Making use of the Rosseland opacity allows us not to make any assumption on the dominant opacity regime at the surface. Since the Rosseland opacity is provided by stellar evolution code, using it does not introduce any additional difficulties. This scaling relation can easily provide a way to correct frequency differences, as shown in Manchon *et al.* (2018).

In order to improve the quality of the patched models, and hopefully of the scaling relation, one could, instead of computing the horizontally averaged stratification, compute the stratification averaged a constant Rosseland optical depth since our relation involve the Rosseland opacity. Furthermore, even if the 1D model and the averaged stratification satisfy the hydrostatic equilibrium, the hydrostatic equilibrium is not necessarily satisfied after the matching of these two model. In order to overcome this problem, it may be more physical to patch with the stratification averaged at constant pressure height scale. This should be devoted to future work

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